

ГОТОВНОСТ НА БЪЛГАРИЯ ДА УЧАСТВА В СИСТЕМАТА НА УНИФИЦИРАН ЗА ЕВРОПЕЙСКИЯ СЪЮЗ ПРОДУКТ ЗА ПЕРСОНАЛНО ПЕНСИОННО ОСИГУРЯВАНЕ

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READINESS OF BULGARIA TO PARTICIPATE IN THE SYSTEM OF A PAN-EUROPEAN PERSONAL PENSION PRODUCT

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Резюме

През последните години капиталовите пенсии увеличават своята роля в развитите страни, а в същото време губят влияние в страни от Централна и Източна Европа, включително и в България. При анализа на проблематиката трябва да се вземе предвид факта, че България е част от Европейския съюз и е необходимо да участва в общи дейности и инициативи. Политика на Европейската комисия е да подкрепя и да насърчава развитието на капиталовите пенсии. Този проблем се отнася и за България, където коефициентът на заместване на пенсията е нисък и съществува натиск върху публичната пенсионна система поради значителен недостиг на пари.

През 2011 г. Европейската комисия стартира дискусия за въвеждане на унифициран продукт за индивидуално пенсионно осигуряване (PEPP). Тази инициатива създава възможности пред страните – членки. Докладът прави анализ на състоянието и готовността на България да участва в процеса на въвеждането на такъв продукт. Разглеждат се проблеми като защо е необходим унифициран продукт за индивидуални пенсии, какво е състоянието на капиталовите пенсии в момента, какви са тенденциите и каква да бъде ролята на капиталовото осигуряване в общата пенсионна система. Докладът търси отговори на въпроси дали е необходим единен продукт и евентуално какво ще е влиянието от неговото въвеждане за България.

Ключови понятия: унифициран продукт за индивидуални пенсии (PEPP), индивидуално пенсионно осигуряване, частни индивидуални пенсии (PPP), интеграция на капиталовото пенсионно осигуряване, дизайн на капиталови пенсии.

JEL Codes: G11, G23, G35

Summary

Capital pensions recently are gaining influence in developed countries and are losing influence in Central and Eastern Europe, including Bulgaria. At the same time Bulgaria is part of the European

Union and has to follow common activities and initiatives. Policy of the European Commission is to support and to urge the development of the capital pensions. This is relevant action for Bulgaria because the pension replacement rate is very low and the public pension system is under pressure of huge cash deficit.

In 2011 the European Commission started discussion for implementing pan-European personal pension product (PEPP). This creates opportunities for member states. The paper deals with the position and readiness of Bulgaria to participate in the process of the latter implementation. Addressed are issues like why is necessary unified personal pension insurance, what is the current situation, what are the tendencies, what is the role of capital pensions in the whole system in Bulgaria. The study searches answers to questions such as whether this product is necessary and what will be the impact for Bulgarian pension system.

Key words: pan-European personal pension product (PEPP), individual pension insurance, private personal pensions (PPP), capital pension integration, capital pension design.

JEL Codes: G11, G23, G35

Introduction

The current study is motivated by desire for detailed analysis of personal pension insurance in Bulgaria considering the potential implementation at EU level of unified individual retirement product. This insurance aims at increasing the retirement security of old persons. The forces at EU level for developing this insurance comes after various factors as low pension replacement rate, shift from DB to DC, aging of population, pressure on public pension systems and desire for capital market development.

The aims of the research are reached through the following four steps: analysis of the reasons for European Commission (EC) initiative for implementation of PEPP; description of the proposed features of the product; examination of the current situation in Bulgaria; setting problems and pointing directions for solutions and measures.

Why single EU market for personal pensions

Pension systems design in EU are under the decisions of the local governments. Nevertheless, pension income inequalities are an obstacle for EU development. Also the share of pension expenditure from Gross Domestic Product (GDP) varies significantly for member states¹. Different pension regimes pose impediments for cross-border movements of workers and citizens. Low interest rate environment requires more and more long-term money. Public pension systems are under pressure to decrease the expenses in order to reduce the public debt and the state budget deficit². At the same time the pension replaces small part of the working salary in many EU countries. The pension replacement coefficient (pension compared to salary) for the year of 2015 is shown in the following chart.

¹ The share of pension expenditure from local GDP varies from 7% up to 15% in 2015 member states with average 11%, according to Eurostat. The projection for 2060 is to widen the gap up to 19% in some countries and 13% EU average.

² European Commission: The 2015 Pension Adequacy report, 2015 p.1.

Chart 1

Source: Eurostat, <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>

As seen in the chart the pension replacement ratio in sixteen member-states are below 60% which is considered as a minimum target level. Among these countries are seven representatives from CEE region – Croatia, Bulgaria, Latvia, Estonia, Slovenia, Lithuania and Czech Republic. The difference between the target and real rate is the *pension gap*. This gap cannot be met by increase in the expenses for public pensions as percentage of GDP.

The EC sets as a milestone **reaching adequate and sustainable pensions**. The Commission states that among the proposed measures is the development of capital pensions. Under *capital pensions* the funds are accumulated during the working life of the person and the size of the pension is dependent on the sum accumulated. One way for increasing the role of capital pensions is the latest development of *occupational pension schemes*. These are schemes related with the workplace of the person. Usually the pension plan is designed or chosen by the employer and the employer is the sponsor of the plan. Occupational pension insurance is well developed in countries with strong and long existing companies. Examples are Germany, UK, Netherlands, Denmark, Belgium and Ireland. Occupational schemes are not developed in most of the member states from CEE – Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, Poland, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Baltic countries – Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia. Concerning occupational pensions there is common EU legislation – IORP directive.

At the same time in 22 out of 25 member states³ there are existing forms of *individual capital pension insurance*. Under these schemes the insurance is decided by the employee who is choosing the amount of contribution, the beginning, the period of insurance and the pension plan. The estimated assets of personal pensions under management are over one trillion Euro. The EC comes to a conclusion that personal pensions are *an issue of European concern*. The EC estimates that there are 72 different types of individual pensions. **For these individual pensions there is no common legislation within the EU.**

³ The number of respondents in EIOPA survey on personal pensions among Member states. EIOPA notes a stark concentration of asset values in NL, UK and BE. The highest number of contracts is issued in Germany – more than 10 million contracts.

One of the reasons for *single* market comes from the many **market failures** in different areas as the fragmented market of personal pensions prevents economies of scale and growth potential. Another reason is the **asymmetric information** that sets the consumers in a weaker position compared to the pension administrator and the asset manager.

The European Insurance and Occupational Pension Authority (EIOPA, the combined body for supervision of insurance and pensions at EU level) sees the PEPP implementation as a tool to improve the current personal pensions. Another set of reasons can be found in search of **improving performance and efficiency**. Good performance and efficiency are considered to be reached after low costs, good asset management results, mitigating the risks of conflict and economies of scale. Decreased costs and good investment results are associated with good corporate governance. Better governed pension funds outperformed poorly governed funds by 2.4 per cent per annum⁴ (Capelle et al, 2008). Other studies have confirmed this link (Ambachtsheer et al, 2006; Ambachtsheer et al, 2007; Clark et al, 2007; and Clark and Urwin, 2007).

PEPP features

In order to reach the goals EIOPA is considering that the *new product has to be more attractive to consumers*. What are the main features of personal pensions and PEPP?

In EU level personal pensions, PPPs⁵ (personal pension products) and PEPP, are understood as products established on the basis of individual membership and sold on a retail basis. **Basic characteristics of personal pension products** are⁶: individual membership; payment of contributions to an individual account; explicit retirement objective – set in legal basis; the early withdrawal of accumulated capital is limited or penalized; providers are private entities and PPPs are funded.

The **Pan-European Personal Pensions Product (PEPP)** is defined with the following characteristics⁷: a) providing *information* in standardized form based on KID⁸ forms among PRIIPs framework; b) standardized *investment choices* with one core default option; c) regulated, flexible, biometric and financial *guarantees*; d) regulated, flexible *limits on cost and charges*; e) regulated, flexible switching and *transfer of funds* and f) no specification of *decumulation* options.

So the description of PEPP focuses on 6 areas such as provided information, asset management, guarantees, costs, transfers and payment phase. All these features are based on long discussions. EIOPA carried public consultation and received industry feedback. It is

⁴ EIOPA: Towards an EU single market for personal pensions: An EIOPA Preliminary Report to COM, 2014, p. 6-7

⁵ The top five member states with highest assets in PPPs are Netherlands, United Kingdom, Belgium, Spain and Sweden, EIOPA database.

⁶ EIOPA's advice on the development of an EU-single market for personal pension products (PPP). EIOPA 16/457. 2016, p.10

⁷ EIOPA's advice on the development of an EU-single market for personal pension products (PPP). EIOPA 16/457. 2016, p.5

⁸ See Regulation (EU) No 1286/2014 on Key Information Documents for Packaged Retail and Insurance-based Investment Products. EIOPA states that during the consultations on PPPs and PEPP many stakeholders supported the proposition that the starting point for disclosure during the pre-contractual phase would be PRIIPs KID.

good that there is no full standardization of PEPP. Full standardization will lead to significant amendments to existing national regimes some of them leading to unattractiveness to providers.

During the discussions there are some proposals that will be considered in future stages. For example the existence of minimum holding periods. From one hand it is a prerequisite for improvement the results of the insurance. On the other hand, it creates an obstacle consumers to buy the product. Most of the consumers are short term orientated and minimum holding periods decrease the liquidity of the undertaking.

Behind the flexibility of costs limits is the idea for setting caps at least for the default investment option. The comparison between the products will be enabled with the development of a common EU standard defined level of a total expense ratio (TER).

The potential *obstacles* for common regime in terms of product are restrictions on investments in foreign currencies, limitations on transferability, differences in taxation and contract law. There is no EU legislation⁹ on the taxation of pensions. Most Member States employ the EET system or ETT principle, but the other variants such as TET, TEE and EEE exists, nevertheless less common. It is logical that the regime for the existing personal pensions to apply for the new PEPP product.

Another important point are the guarantees¹⁰ implied in the product. Common understanding is that the guarantees should be allowed yet not be required. We have to bear in mind that the guarantees are important for entity's obligations, technical provisions and capital requirements. Increased requirement as a mandatory element will be huge obstacle for implementing new regime at EU level.

Another line for decreasing the costs is the introduction of *product passport* for PEPP. It can function through a centralized EU register and means a free offer of PEPP in all member states upon authorization.

Good corporate governance is seen as an instrument for improved asset management results, prerequisites for transparency and trust. Governance encompasses fit and proper management, functions for risk management, actuarial tasks, internal control, compliance and audit, remuneration policy, self-risk assessment, depositories and others. The problem is that following all these principles is leading to higher costs. So there has to be balance between these two elements.

After analyzing the reasons of PEPP and its most supported features what are the possibilities to implement the new rules. The possibilities can be summarized to two: the introduction of a 2nd regime PPP (PEPP) or the improvement the regulation of all PPPs. **EIOPA recommends the introduction of new regime** – the so called 2nd regime PPP. It means¹¹ to create a standardized Pan-European Personal Pension Product (PEPP) through separate set of EU rules that do not replace current and national rules but are instead an optional alternative to the latter. The second option means rules set out in a Directive and harmonization of current and national PPP requirements. This at the moment is considered as more unrealistic taking into

⁹ European Commission: Pension taxation. E – Exempt from taxation, T – under Taxation. Applied for the three elements: contributions, distributed investment income and benefits.

¹⁰ Usually the guarantees are financial, biometric, performance-related or against inflation.

¹¹ EIOPA's advice on the development of an EU-single market for personal pension products (PPP). EIOPA 16/457. 2016, p. 13

account potential disapproval of many member states.

There is a great logic that the impact of such new regime will be bigger for countries like Bulgaria. This is statement that is supported by EIOPA¹² with the argument that occupational pension schemes are less developed in such member states.

Readiness of Bulgaria

Bulgaria is among the countries that has launched personal schemes since 1994. In the light of PEPP the main questions are whether these schemes are attractive for clients and whether they are consistent with EC/EIOPA proposed new regime.

Capital pensions are part of the whole pension system. At the moment the PAYG pension is the predominant pensionable income. The size of the pensions in the country are very low. The pension replacement ratio is 41% which is second lowest in EU¹³ (see Chart 1). In absolute values the average pension is 164 Euro¹⁴. At the same time the State Budget supplies more than 50% of the expenses for PAYG pension. This creates uncertainty for the future growth of the size of the pension. Another issue is negative demographic tendencies in Bulgaria – negative natural growth of the population and young people departure. As a result Bulgaria is registering one of the greatest proportion of people aged 65 and over as a percentage of the total population in EU (see Chart 2 below).

Chart 2

Source: Eurostat, <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tps00028>

The high proportion of old people leads to pressure on the state budget for financing the PAYG pensions – decreasing number of workers has to finance the pensions of increasing number of pensioners. As a consequence - the room for pension increase is very limited. At

¹² EIOPA’s advice on the development of an EU-single market for personal pension products (PPP). EIOPA 16/457. 2016. p.8

¹³ Eurostat. <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>. Only Croatia has lower ratio of 40%.

¹⁴ As of the end of 2015. Figures from National Social Security Institute, www.nssi.bg

this situation the increase of the role of private pension seems the best way. From one hand, the personal private pension will be added to the PAYG pension and it will lead to increase of the pension replacement rate. On the other hand, private pension is related with the personal contribution to the fund and this is the way to boost the interest for system's participation. The latter is also considered as an element of the measures against grey incomes.

Existing from 23 years personal pension insurance is not yet well developed in Bulgaria. The number of insured is 600 thousands with accumulated assets from 880 mln. BGN. There is no information neither from FSC nor from pension administrators for the number of persons with personal contribution and active contract. Based on some assumptions the active insured with personal VPF can be estimated at 100 000¹⁵ people and average annual contribution of 800 BGN. This number is very low compared to number of working population of 3 032 000 people. The low coverage is a problem to efficiency. The cost are spread on small number of insured and low volume of assets. In addition, small pension funds creates additional risks for insured. The reasons for this are different and most of them are outside the pension industry (for example: strong attitude to save in bank deposits; flat tax rate of 10% on personal incomes; uncertainty for working incomes; two very strong financial crisis in 1996-1997 and 2007-2008 and others).

Based on the analysis so far we can derive the conclusion that the personal pension insurance in Bulgaria has to be extended. How it could happen, taking into account PEPP initiative, we can say after comparing the existing regulation of individual insurance in Voluntary Pension Fund (VPF) with the basic characteristics of the proposed new regime of PEPP.

Comparison between individual insurance in Bulgaria/VPF and proposed PEPP

Table № 1

feature	individual VPF	PEPP
provided information	specified requirements	KIDs in PRIIPs
investment choices	no	yes, incl. default option
pension vehicle	fund	fund
administrator - accumulation	pension insurance company	under national rules
administrator - decumulation	pension insurance company	under national rules
guarantees	no	flexible
caps on charges	yes, in broad ranges	yes
decumulation options	flexible	flexible
transfer of funds	yes	yes
tax treatment	EEE	under national rules
type of scheme	DC	DC

¹⁵ Author's estimations based on statistics for voluntary pension insurance from FSC

design	funded	funded
money inheritance	yes	yes, not specified
right of early withdrawal	yes	penalized
right of freedom of service	no	yes

Source: The author

The comparison is showing that the **problematic discrepancies** between VPF and PEPP are in limited scope – only in three areas: the institutions that can be pension administrators; sanctions or certain limits for early withdrawal and tax regime of the insurance. Other areas are identical or similar – DC scheme, funded insurance, pension fund as a vehicle, transfer of funds, decumulation options and others. The differences in other two areas (investment options and guarantees) can be solved with slightly changes in the legislation. A challenge for the Bulgarian market will be the implementation of the principle of right of freedom of service. Funds registered in other EU member states can steal the wealthy clients of local companies and thus further to decrease the coverage of personal insurance.

In Bulgaria pension administrator can be only one institution – the pension insurance company. In other EU countries banks, asset managers or life insurance companies are given some activities – from selling, registering, assets managing servicing to pension payment. The vast majority of the personal pension arrangements in EU are issued and managed by life insurance undertakings.

Early withdrawal of personal assets in Bulgaria is without limit which is not the case in many EU countries. Also different is the applied tax regime - for VPF is in force EEE tax regime. That means the contributions are tax exempt to certain amounts, the investment income is exempt as well as the pension.

Another hurdle will be how to make these pension products to become more attractive to consumers, i.e. potential pension savers, and more cost effective, as well as more compatible with increased mobility of European citizens. Additionally, improving consumer information and protection in voluntary personal retirement savings is necessary to enhance consumers' confidence in those products. Before future changes in the legislation it has to be assessed the public opinion for individual pensions in Bulgaria. This opinion has to be taken in mind in the proposed changes in the legislation. Examples of such studies are in UK (2011) and Italy (2013) where there are answers why consumers do not buy personal pensions.

Study about the consumer perceptions is step to set the client in focus. This has to be the regulatory policy and the strategy of the pension administrator. For example, one important fact for the market of financial products is connected with the provided information – the way and the level. There is a behavioral obstacle for buying retirement products – people has *present bias orientation*. In order to overcome this fact there are guidelines for presenting information to clients that has to make decision for buying retirement products¹⁶. For example, recommended are *interactive automated tools*. Another solution is following the *layering approach* - using layers of information. First layer are answers to key questions. Second layer are answers to further questions and legal information.

¹⁶ EIOPA: Good practices on information provision for DC schemes, enabling occupational DC scheme members to plan for retirement, 2013. (known as Max report, Max was used as an average consumer)

In terms of costs it is recommended development of the non-advised distribution – mainly on-line sales. It will work in environment of standardized products and in existence of default option. Responsibility of the regulator is to keep the *charges* low. It is a fact that the size of charges varies significantly¹⁷ among countries. High charges erode the trust of clients and politicians.

Concentration of most of the activities in single body can help for decreasing charges and low costs. Stimulation of the *competition* keeps alert the pension companies and is a prerequisite for better service for the insured persons.

In terms of asset management there is need of *diversification* geographically and by asset class. The regulators have to take into account the importance of the *default funds*. *Benchmarks* lead to greater transparency. Most experts accept as an appropriate *investment result* the target of inflation + 3%.

Conclusion

Following the analysis above it can be concluded that PEPP is a good EC initiative. It focuses the attention of how to decide the problem with pension gap in EU countries. It creates good environment for discussion how to increase the role of capital pensions and how to improve the awareness of the positive elements of capital pension insurance. The proposed PEPP features lays path for easy implementation of the new regime. It creates broad picture with combination between standardized and flexible characteristics. This initiative will lead to further development of common framework for personal pension in EU.

Bulgaria has good base framework for personal pensions in existing Voluntary pension fund. The discrepancies with PEPP can be matched with not fundamental changes in the national legislation. For these changes there is a need for incentive from outside the country. In fact the country has not yet adopted the policy of adequate and sustainable pensions which is the strategy in the EU level. It is responsibility of the government to create a framework for affordable, transparent and cost-effective retirement product.

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